

Research Article

Processing and Quality Evaluation of Additive Manufacturing Monolayer Specimens

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Although its importance has increased significantly, Additive Manufacturing is not yet a fully accepted industrial manufacturing process for load-carrying parts. The future success of the process group depends on its standardization. This work proposes a methodology for the design, manufacturing, and quality evaluation of specimens manufactured by Fused Layer Modeling that are composed of only one layer (so-called monolayers). The processing methodology and properties of monolayers have not been studied systematically yet. A first systematic design of monolayers for mechanical testing is presented. Rectangular and circular monolayers adapted to the loads of tensile and compression testing are manufactured using different trajectory strategies. Frequently occurring macro- and microgeometrical defects are evaluated and categorized in order to optimize the part quality. This work also studies the effect of some manufacturing parameters such as the gap between print head and machine bed, trajectory strategy, bed leveling, and temperatures on part quality. The most suitable specimens are tested mechanically in tensile or compression tests. In the case of study, tensile strength values are only 8.6% lower than the values for reference tests on the unextruded filament. However, the properties deviate more strongly for compression tests which may be due to the selected specimen geometry.

1. Introduction

Additive Manufacturing (AM) is gaining importance for the manufacturing not only of prototypes and tools, but also for serial load-carrying parts [1, 2]. It is even starting to replace conventional manufacturing processes where complex parts with small lead-time and lot sizes are needed, more so if otherwise specialized tools would be needed [3, 4]. While AM was invented more than twenty years ago under the term Rapid Prototyping [4], the market interest has only recently increased strongly with AM now producing about 29% of final parts [1].

AM technologies are manufacturing processes which create the physical part by adding material incrementally based on digital information. This information is provided

via a three-dimensional CAD-model that is converted to a tessellated format and sliced virtually [5] (Figure 1).

This way of obtaining a part leads to new design possibilities and can therefore produce parts with a very high stiffness-to-weight-ratio [4].

Parts manufactured with track-based AM processes are generally anisotropic within and between layers [4, 6–8]. For Fused Layer Manufacturing (FLM), the single tracks and layers (monolayers) are similar to the fibers and layers that are part of laminated fiber-reinforced composite materials [9]. The binding between the tracks or fibers and between layers has a strong influence on the properties of the multilayer part both for fiber-reinforced composites and for parts manufactured using a track-based AM process (such as Electron Beam Melting, Fused Layer Manufacturing, or Stereolithography)

tensile strength values that are only 8.6% lower than the values for reference tests on the raw material.

Future works should be focused on the design of testing procedures and standard specimens for each AM process and material. They should correspond to the basic mechanic loads. Also, developing multifunctional specimens and tests for a group of similar AM processes might be recommendable, studying the similarities in mechanical behavior and material processing for different AM processes, machines, and materials.

A deeper understanding of the behavior and properties of single tracks, monolayers, multilayer parts, and their relationship is needed. Also, the methodology that was proposed in this work may be applied to additively manufactured parts with internal reinforcements or microstructures.

Competing Interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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